

ISic1514

I.Sicily inscription 1514

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

plaque

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Catacomb of S.Giovanni

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Catacomba di San Giovanni

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Οὔτος [ὁ] τόπος

2. διαφέρει

3. Πελεγρίνου

4. φώλωνος

Apparatus

text of Agnello 1953

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645014

Bibliography

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-18): ISic1514. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI
edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4354251>